

Multiculturalism and Entrepreneurial Engagement Levels Among Early-Stage Firms

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Abstract: This paper has as objective to identify the determinants of opportunity recognition among early-stage firms in a multicultural environment. Given that most research works agreed that, individuals' locus of control, need for achievement, entrepreneurial alertness and risk tolerance permit the acquisition of knowledge; the knowledge spill-over theory holds that acquired knowledge still remains potentially viable for the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities. The independent variables of this study consist of; general culture awareness, multicultural efficacy, multi fluency, acceptance, broad role repertoire and groundedness. To obtain data for the study, a questionnaire was administered to 120 respondents' owner-managers of micro and small early-stage enterprises and the ordered probit model was used to analyze the data. The results indicated that entrepreneurial alertness is a major determinant factor for increasing the zeal to acquire multicultural competencies. Also, general culture awareness, multi fluency, multicultural efficacy and broad role repertoire prove their existential effect though having a relative meaning or lesser degree of importance on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities. This confirm the positive contribution that multicultural competencies have on entrepreneurial opportunity recognition. From our findings, we recommend that owner-managers of young businesses at early-stage should develop their existing knowledge in business operations through acquiring multicultural competencies. This will help increase the effectiveness of growth expectations for their young businesses through the recognition of more potential entrepreneurial opportunities.

Keywords: Knowledge spill-over, Entrepreneurial opportunity recognition, Multicultural competencies, Early-stage firms

I. Introduction

According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Report by Slavica et al. (2014), the cultural diverse nature of a country given its people or inhabitants is of importance if well exploited. This can help reinforce the relationship between individuals' cognitive and psychological traits and operational entrepreneurship given abilities-demand fit. Entry into an entrepreneurial activity given the unstructured and dynamic nature of the environment as Jonason et al. (2010) put it, would apparently give an attractive face lift to entrepreneurship.

The notion of abilities-demand fit as an element of human capital fostering entrepreneurial actions describes human behaviour for which individuals turn to have limited intentional control (Ajzen, 1991; Bar-on and Ensley, 2006). This is because entrepreneurial behaviour most at times rely on external happenings which are beyond individuals' scope of control. Baron and Markman (2004) established that, engaging into an entrepreneurial activity can be seen as a job. Hence, with the above assertion, it can be posited that individuals should add value to their abilities-demand fit by making a shift from being prone of becoming entrepreneurs by simply looking for an activity or venture that fits their personality traits (Shane et al., 2010). Harboring such a perception of fit by individuals turn to have a negative effect on human capital (competencies) thus, allowing the individual entrepreneur to look at his/her job to seem stressful and more demanding. This allows them to put in more abilities, skills, knowledge and other experiences (KSAOs) that might help moderate riskiness thereby giving room for satisfaction, commitment and motivation in exercising the entrepreneurial venture.

According to Yeasmin (2016) and Aleksandra (2014); entrepreneurship and intercultural participation represent a better cohesion for the better usage of human capital given the prevailing socio-economic problems being that of rising unemployment rates most especially in developing economies with Cameroon not left out.

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Cameroon constitute most of the country's enterprises composed of sectors such as; transformation, agriculture and animal husbandry, general commerce, construction and public works and with Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) being the most recent (CFCE, 2015). According to the Research and Analysis Centre on the Economic and Social Policies of Cameroon (CAMERCAP-PARC); 61,366 SMEs were created between 2010 and 2016 in Cameroon. 59,200 of the enterprises were local enterprises while 2,166 from abroad. Going by the CAMERCAP-PARC records in May 2016; 72.24 per cent of the enterprises are no longer in existence as per statistics from the taxation department database. Additionally, the 2016 annual statistics of the Ministry of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, Social Economy and Handicraft (MINPMEESA) established that; SMEs are the fundamental drivers for economic growth but, contributed only 36 per cent to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Mbonteh (2017) suggested in their study that, in becoming an emerging country, SMEs in Cameroon are required to increase their contribution to the GDP to about 50 per cent. CAMERCAP-PARC in its 2016 study demonstrated also that 66.43 per cent of SMEs in the transformation sector, 46.84 per cent in Agriculture, 31.64 per cent in general Commerce, 28.16 per cent in Associations and training and 25.86 per cent of enterprises in the construction and public works sectors survive the challenges affecting the likelihood of success at early-stage.

Despite the creation of all these new enterprises with majority being very small enterprises (VSE), many are said to be disappearing from existence particularly at their early-stage of activity. Going by the CAMERCAP-PARC records in May 2016; 72.24 per cent of the enterprises are no longer in existence as per statistics from the taxation department database. With the many entrepreneurial businesses face with so many difficulties upon start-up, researchers have investigated and identified the vulnerability of newness (Stinch-Combe, 1965), alongside some financial constraints as reasons for entrepreneurial failure (Cope, 2011; Freeman et al., 1983; Shepherd et al., 2011).

Prior works targeting individual opportunity recognition behaviour, alongside their innovation performance ability had already been included in research works both as subsets and principal objective (Jong et al., 2011; Bindl and Parker, 2010). Given the multicultural nature of an environment like Cameroon, we posit that; acquiring multicultural competencies will contribute to our understanding of factors affecting opportunity recognition among owner-managers of young micro and small enterprises, as well as the determinants of innovation performance in becoming established businesses. This will help practitioners to better reconstruct their entrepreneurial orientation. It will also predispose entrepreneurs to identify more potential opportunities having innovative openings.

According to Acs et al. (2009); the knowledge spill over theory of entrepreneurship suggests that; investing in knowledge acquisition by newly created firms and research institutes such as universities will engender entrepreneurial opportunities given that not all new knowledge will be exploited by these firms for financial gains. As Arrow (1962) highlights in their research study, built-in new knowledge is uncertain and asymmetric in nature. As such, newly created firms and research institutes find it difficult to recognize and act on all the knowledge they have invested to acquire. Acquired knowledge might be perceived to be a potentially useful idea but; the decision-making body of the firm or the individual may consider it as not being valuable. The knowledge filter as per the knowledge spill over theory is defined as "the extent to which new knowledge remains uncommercialized by the structure that generates the knowledge." This makes the knowledge to remain potentially viable for which more entrepreneurial opportunities can still be extracted. Going after uncommercialized residual of acquired knowledge by newly created firms or business; pursuing entrepreneurial venture in such a context makes reference to knowledge spillovers. Better still, knowledge spillovers serve as a key determinant for entrepreneurial activity (Acs et al., 2004).

Based on this theory, we suggest that; by acquiring multicultural competencies given the multicultural nature of a territory, individuals will be privileged to acquire multiple new knowledge, skills, abilities and other experiences (Al-Shammari, 2018; Bell and Harrison, 1996). By exploiting these new knowledge which might be an idea vested with potentials; not only will the entrepreneur be exposed to new entrepreneurial opportunities but also, the extent to which these new knowledge remain uncommercialized will serve as a key determinant for the growth of entrepreneurial activity especially newly created businesses or firms still at their early years of existence. In summary, the following hypotheses are put forth:

H1. Entrepreneurial alertness increases the zeal to acquire multicultural competencies

H2. Openness to multicultural competencies has a positive and significant effect on individuals' potentials to recognize more entrepreneurial opportunities

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H2a. General culture awareness significantly increases the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities

H2b. Multi fluency has a significant positive effect on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities

H2c. Multicultural efficacy has a positive and significant effect on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities

H2d. Broad role repertoire significantly increases the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities

In accomplishing the objective of this research being to assess the impact of acquiring multicultural competencies on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities, we first review literature on entrepreneurship and psychological traits and integrate them into identifying more entrepreneurial opportunities in a multicultural environment. Secondly, literature on the role of the entrepreneur as an individual in identifying more entrepreneurial opportunities in a multicultural setting will be discussed. Demonstrations made will be to show how, by acquiring multicultural competencies in a multicultural environment; individuals' entrepreneurial behaviour given their entrepreneurial orientations is being enhanced. This is made possible viewing the knowledge spill-over theory whereby, acquired knowledge is said to always be potentially viable for commercial benefit (Aleksandra, 2014; Ardichvili et al., 2003; Audretsch et al., 2010). Thirdly, research models and methods will be spelt out from where analyses will be made giving rise to results and conclusions drawn on the evidence that suggest the significance of multicultural competencies acquisition on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities having innovative potentials, the roots for better engagement levels for new ventures.

II. Literature Review

Entrepreneurial alertness is posited in entrepreneurship as the discovery and exploitation of opportunities and resources in an economy moving towards equilibrium (Kirzner, 1997, 2009). Kirzner suggested that the main feature of entrepreneurial alertness is the quest for information by the entrepreneur implanted in them as an entrepreneurial behaviour. The first empirical study on the theory of alertness was carried out by Kaish and Gilad in 1991. The authors found that, entrepreneurs used information differently and were more alert to opportunities due to their possession of knowledge and information. We can suggest here in line with Kirzner that; by utilizing the acquired information to initiate and build business potentials, entrepreneurs tend to ameliorate their ability of being able to recognize more entrepreneurial opportunities in line with customers' problems (Fiet, 2002; Tang et al, 2012).

Intercultural interactions are characterized by humane oriented and performance oriented conditions that help in either strengthening or shrinking the life cycle of opportunity recognition. Previous research argued that intercultural interactions through intercultural dimensions created an added value to individuals' entrepreneurial orientation behaviour (Aleksandra, 2014). In the era of new knowledge acquisition, multicultural competencies, which would dominate the growth of a firm, is one of the important assets to boost the growth and development of young micro and small ventures into well established businesses. Moreover, there exist a positive relationship between mono cultural and bicultural competencies and entrepreneurship (Al-Shammari and Alshammari, 2018; Bell and Harrison, 1996; LaFromboise, 2010). Furthermore, general culture awareness, bicultural efficacy, dual fluency, acceptance, broad role repertoire and groundedness of business operators have a positive effect on entrepreneurial orientation behaviour on the growth of business activities (Al-Shammari and Alshammari, 2018).

Given research carried out by Robles and Cordero-Guzmán (2007), it was discovered that the low level of education of the Latin Americans who form the largest bicultural minority in the United States might appear to be the driving force toward self-employment. It was as well discovered that the lack of financial means (both formal and informal access to capital) acted as barriers to the creation of businesses and enhancing their development; explaining the reason behind the concentration of activities in the service domain. Even though this study was not out to address the role of multiculturalism on entrepreneurial opportunity recognition and evaluation leading to innovation performance, it however throws more light on the required package needed among multicultural individuals in business creation and growth. This study called for research that can unveil the social aspect and the self-employment drive given a multicultural background. This study can be used as a stepping stone on which we can base our arguments to demonstrate the role of multiculturalism (multicultural skills, knowledge, abilities and other experiences) in establishing entrepreneurial behaviours that will enlighten individuals to perceive faster entrepreneurial opportunities that are better off in guaranteeing innovation performance in their communities and local areas.

2.1 Multicultural Competencies in Entrepreneurship

Carrying out research on multiculturalism into entrepreneurship literature is a projected angle of knowledge that will permit boosting entrepreneurship theory across a multi-facet of cultures thus, building our understanding on the role of multiculturalism in opportunity recognition and exploitation leading to innovation performance ensuring the success of business ventures at their early-stage of operation (Al Shammari and Al-Shammari, 2018). Regarding biculturalism, much focus had been placed on the negative aspects of biculturalism; for example, identity conflict and stress (Fordham, 1988; Sung, 1985). Many research works have paid more attention on the relevance of biculturalism in pursuing entrepreneurial activities, with emphasis being placed on the human resource literature from an international perspective. It can be argued from a bicultural viewpoint according to Bell and Harrison (1996) that multicultural experiences can promote the effectiveness and success potentials of early-stage entrepreneurial activity given individuals’ diverse cognitive abilities, dark triads and mixed cultural foundations(Fouda et al., 2015). Figure 1 below gives us a representation of the necessities for entrepreneurial opportunities and success in a multicultural setting.

MULTICULTURAL COMPETENCIES IMPLICATIONS ON ENTREPRENEURIAL POTENTIALS FOR OPPORTUNITY IDENTIFICATION		
Multiculturalcompetencies	Definition	Necessities for entrepreneurial potentials for opportunities and success
General culture awareness (GCA)	Knowledge of multiple cultures’ beliefs and values	Creates multiple thoughts, avenues, perceptions and several separated pieces of information, a means of building information processing abilities in individuals.
Multiculturalefficacy (ME)	Sureness that one can live efficaciously among the multiple cultural groups without compromising one’s cultural identity	Creates psychological stability which helps individuals having high dark triads to adjust some of their actions and behaviours, though might create conflicting views.
Multi fluency (MF)	Ability to communicate effectively with the multiple cultural groups	Enhances knowledge, skills, abilities and other experiences of individuals
Acceptance (A)	Positive attitudes toward the multiple cultural groups	Installs acceptance, legitimacy, and contributes in promoting communication with diverse cultures thus, enabling individuals to acquire varying know-how and use different lenses in perceiving reality.
Broad rolerepetoire (BRR)	Having a continuous distinguishable acceptable behaviours towards the multiple cultural groups	Enhances legitimacy and acceptance
Groundedness (G)	Unchanging social networks in the multiple cultural groups	Reinforces ties with the public and enhances opportunities given multiple social networks

Figure 1: Multiculturalism and opportunity identification

Source: author’s conception

III. Research models and methods

3.1 Data

This study uses data collection built on questionnaire and conducted through the researcher's effort aimed at assessing how individual entrepreneurs exploit their multicultural environment. Through this, we included the extent to which individual entrepreneurs' psychological traits affect multicultural competencies. In particular, young business owners at early-stage of entrepreneurial activity formed the target of our study (that is, businesses existing for less than 5 years). Branches of activity both formal and informal from the agricultural (farming, fishing and rearing of animals), general commerce, industrial activity (tailoring, building, carpentry and car repairs) and services were included. Such heterogeneity would bring forth a meaningful aggregation of data, permitting a better assessment of the effect of multicultural competencies on more entrepreneurial opportunity recognition being the purpose of the current research study.

Data were collected from very small and small business owners at various levels of activity within the targeted firms' description, with the use of questionnaire-based survey. The first part of the survey consisted of the demographic variables pertaining to the targeted businesses while; the second part was built on descriptive variables on psychological traits, multicultural competencies, entrepreneurial opportunity recognition and innovative performance. Incentives were given for survey completion. Although with the wide range of very small and small business establishments, a sample of convenience appeared to be appropriate for this study. The research design for this study is in line with Hales' (2005) study of first line managers.

A total of 120 firms were reached out with our research tool. Out of the 120 questionnaire administered, 120 were received from the multiple respondents, giving a response rate of 100%. The survey contained several measures for which respondents needed to give their opinion. The buildup measures represent complete data on the relevant research variables. Owner managers of firms were chosen as key informants because the research variables built up for this study needed data from individual entrepreneurs involve in the day-to-day running of their businesses (Hambrick, 1981).

3.2 Measurement

The dependent variable in our study is opportunity recognition. It was measured by asking respondent to indicate clearly their view on a 4-point, Likert-type scale (ranging from [1=] "No new good opportunity" to [4=] "5 more new growth opportunity"). The degree of importance was apportioned based on the following criteria: the number of new good opportunities for growth recognized, number of opportunities from the market to which your enterprise was apt in meeting the needs and the number of new products or services developed and brought to the market.

The multicultural competencies assessment instrument which we developed while making reference to cultures and variations in personality traits related to entrepreneurial behaviour (Al Shammari and Al-Shammari, 2018; Neubaum, 2016b; Omorede et al., 2015), was used to measure the six independent variables under study being: general culture awareness, multicultural efficacy, multi fluency, acceptance, broad role repertoire and groundedness. Consistent with previous research on entrepreneurs' alertness to make profit through spotting out opportunities (Kirzner, 1997; Schumpeter, 1942; Shane, 2000); factor analysis of the current data supports the theoretical structure of the instrument's scale. All independent variables items were evaluated on five point, Likert-type scales spread from "strongly disagree" (= 1) to "strongly agree" (= 5). A stronger influence of multicultural competencies is indicated by a higher mean scale value of the measured criteria.

The control variables included in the current study consist of: age, level of education, branch of activity and employment preference. The firm size in terms of employees was measured with respect to the set of criteria for classifying enterprises from law 2010/001 of April 13, 2010. The respondents' age bracket was built on the consideration of the working age in the country with some extension beyond the retirement age.

As a means of handling complexity in individuals' understanding of questions and also, testing the scales; a pre-testing of questionnaire was carried out on ten (10) owner-managers of very small and small businesses. Our objective being to see how owner-managers of new businesses given their environmental context, adopt strategic entrepreneurship

behaviour. The pre-test of questionnaire permitted some adjustments to be made to facilitate the attainment of the overall objective of the study.

3.3 model specification

The main function of our research study holds that;

$$y = x_i\alpha + \varepsilon \tag{1}$$

Where; y = entrepreneurial opportunity recognition, x_i = multicultural competencies of 'i' owner managers of micro and small enterprises with 'i' ranging from 1 to 120, and α = entrepreneurial alertness. "ε" from our model represents the control variables of this study being; Age, Level of education, Branch of activity, Employment preference.

$$OR = f(MC) \tag{2}$$

Where OR = Opportunity Recognition and MC = Multicultural Competencies

MC can be decompose into 6 (six) separate variables as indicated in equation 3 below.

$$OR = f(GCA, ME, MF, A, BRR, G) \tag{3}$$

While the econometric equation is of the form

$$OR = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1GCA + \alpha_2ME + \alpha_3MF + \alpha_4A + \alpha_5BRR + \alpha_6G + \varepsilon \tag{4}$$

By building such a function, it will permit that the individual effect of each variable of multicultural competencies on opportunity recognition be captured. Additionally, a composite effect of multicultural competencies on opportunity recognition will be captured as well. The model used in carrying out our analysis is the Ordered Probit model whereby; probit regressions on marginal effects over pooled data were used. This model was chosen given the fact that; our dependent variable (multicultural competencies) captures human behaviour. More specifically, Ordered Probit model was preferred given that; questions directed to capture owner-managers' response regarding multicultural competencies; were spread over several scales being: strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree. Figure 2 below is a representation of the hypothesized model for this study.

Figure 2: Hypothesized model
Source: author’s conception

IV. Results and Discussions

H1. Entrepreneurial alertness increases the zeal to acquire multicultural competencies

VARIABLES	(1) Marginal effects
Entrepreneurial alertness	0.00181** (0.00362)
Education	0.146** (0.105)
Age	0.0286 (0.175)
Branch of activity	0.0116 (0.120)
Employment option	-0.122** (0.137)
Observations	120

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Entrepreneurial alertness is 0.2 percentage points more likely to report an increase zeal in acquiring multicultural competencies at 0.05 level of significance. Being significant at 0.05 level is a reflection of the much importance this variable represents as an antecedent to the acquisition of multicultural competencies permitting the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities. The average across representing the threshold value stands at 0.00362 with entrepreneurial alertness being positive and significant. This result is in line with Karabulut (2016) research results showing the positive influence of entrepreneurial alertness, a psychological trait of individuals that plays a predominant role on entrepreneurial intentions.

As for the role of the control variables on the relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and the zeal of acquiring multicultural competencies, the level of education showcase a 14.6 percentage points more likely in developing the zeal to acquire multicultural competencies. A unit increase in age increases the chance of acquiring multicultural competencies by 2.9 percentage points. The increase is far below the threshold that stands at 0.175. This lower rate of positive control can be explain by the fact that; most youths between 18-32 years are more focus in becoming civil servant rather than being self-employed. In addition, some persons within this age bracket that are self-employed still manifest the interest to have been a civil servant while running their businesses at the same time. Branch of activity is 1.2 percentage points more likely to building the zeal to acquire multicultural competencies whereas; employment choice decreasing the chance of developing the zeal to acquire multicultural competencies by 12.2 percentage points.

H2. Openness to multicultural competencies has a positive and significant effect on individuals’ potentials to recognize more entrepreneurial opportunities

VARIABLES	(1) Marginal effects
Openness to multicultural competencies	0.0276* (0.0165)
Education	-0.00886 (0.105)
Age	-0.567***

	(0.184)
Branch of activity	-0.252**
	(0.127)
Employment option	0.0594
	(0.141)
Constant cut1	-4.599***
	(1.097)
Constant cut2	-3.639***
	(1.086)
Constant cut3	-2.897***
	(1.080)
Constant cut4	-2.039*
	(1.065)
Constant cut5	-1.491
	(1.055)
Constant cut6	-1.104
	(1.052)
Observations	120

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Openness to multicultural competencies is positive and significant at 0.1 level as it reveals a 2.8 percentage points more likely to report an effect on individuals' potentials in recognizing entrepreneurial opportunities. Its significance level can be boosted through governmental policies put in place to promote the embracement of multicultural KSAOs essential for the growth of firms and businesses. Its positivity is a demonstration of its relevance in selecting and managing potential entrepreneurial opportunities having innovative performance. This is in line with Audretsch (2010) findings on cultural diversity and entrepreneurship where the diversity of people was seen to be more conducive or better still, to have a positive impact on new firm formation.

The level of education, age and branch of activity showcase a decrease chance of influencing the relationship between openness to multicultural competencies to the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities with their respective percentage points being; 0.9, 56.7 and 25.2. The branch of activity though significant, has a negative control over the effect of openness to multicultural competencies on opportunity recognition. Employment preference stands as the only control variable having a positive but not significant percentage point of 5.9 influence, on reconciling differences between individuals' openness to multicultural competencies and the ability to recognize potential entrepreneurial opportunities. This therefore implies, employment choice can be considered as a strong catalyzer in boosting owner managers' openness to multicultural competencies in line with the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities.

H2a. General culture awareness significantly increases the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities

VARIABLES	(1) Marginal effects
General culture awareness	0.0459***
	(0.0738)
Education	-0.0169***
	(0.105)
Age	-0.570***
	(0.191)
Branch of activity	-0.277**
	(0.133)
Employment option	0.00551
	(0.137)
Constant cut1	-4.092***
	(1.096)
Constant cut2	-3.135***
	(1.091)
Constant cut3	-2.404**

	(1.088)
Constant cut4	-1.568
	(1.077)
Constant cut5	-1.024
	(1.067)
Constant cut6	-0.630
	(1.062)
Observations	120

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Regarding general culture awareness significantly increasing the recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities, results show a 4.6 percentage points more likely for general culture awareness to increase the recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities. The portrait increase stands out to be significant at 0.01 level. Its high degree of significance is a reflection of the much importance this variable can contribute for the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities in a multicultural environment. Thus, general culture awareness stands as an ideal breeding ground for owner-managers of micro and small businesses to grow their entrepreneurial oriented new ventures.

The level of education, age and branch of activity given their respective control function represent 1.7, 57 and 27.7 percentage points less likely to stir up the effect of general culture awareness to the recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities. Though with their negativity, the level of education and age demonstrate a high degree of significance (0.01 level), while the branch of activity is also significant at 0.05 level as to increasing the effect of general culture awareness on opportunity recognition. Employment preference tends out to be the lone control factor having a 0.6 percentage points more likely to increase the effect of general culture awareness on opportunity recognition, but is not significant at all the conventional levels of significance.

H2b. Multi fluency has a significant positive effect on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities

VARIABLES	(1) Marginal effects
Multifluency	0.0910*** (0.0558)
education	0.000114 (0.105)
age	-0.539*** (0.183)
Branch of activity	-0.307** (0.123)
Employment option	-0.00379 (0.137)
Constant cut1	-3.178*** (1.053)
Constant cut2	-2.161** (1.048)
Constant cut3	-1.429 (1.046)
Constant cut4	-0.613 (1.036)
Constant cut5	-0.0597 (1.029)
Constant cut6	0.353 (1.028)
Observations	120

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

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Multi fluency seen in our study to be the ability to communicate effectively with multiple cultural groups show a 9.1 percentage points more likely to increase the recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities. Additionally, this variable is of much importance to the recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities given its high level of significance that stands at 0.01 level. The 9.1 percentage points indicate more likelihood for the existence or presence of an irrefutable effect of multi fluency on the recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities. The level of education though not significant at all conventional levels of significance represents a 0.01 percentage points more likely to positively control the effect of multi fluency on individuals' ability in recognizing entrepreneurial opportunities. Age, branch of activity and employment preference all report a decrease chance of reconciling differences between multi fluency and the recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities with their percentage points that stands at 53.9, 30.7 and 0.4. Age and branch of activity are of much importance given their high level of significance (0.01 level), but individuals' choice of employment has a lesser control effect on the existing relationship given its non-significance at all conventional levels of significance.

H2c. Multicultural efficacy has a positive and significant effect on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities

VARIABLES	(1) Marginal effects
Multicultural efficacy	0.260*** (0.0646)
Education	-0.0894 (0.107)
Age	-0.813*** (0.197)
Branch of activity	-0.312** (0.124)
Employment option	-0.0457 (0.138)
Constant cut1	-6.654*** (1.231)
Constant cut2	-5.548*** (1.192)
Constant cut3	-4.774*** (1.184)
Constant cut4	-3.879*** (1.165)
Constant cut5	-3.292*** (1.150)
Constant cut6	-2.884** (1.145)
Observations	120

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Multicultural efficacy from the above analysis reveals a 26 percentage points more likely to report its existential influence on owner-managers of micro and small enterprises recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities. More so, its high level of significance that stands at 0.01 is a demonstration of the high degree of importance this variable has on individuals' ability in recognizing more entrepreneurial opportunities for the growth of their new ventures. The level of education, age, branch of activity and employment preference as control variables reveal 8.9, 81.3, 31.2 and 4.6 percentage points less likely to boost the effect of multicultural efficacy on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities. This results reveal the need for individuals venturing into entrepreneurial activity irrespective of their level of education, age, branch of activity and employment preference; to develop the habit of living together among multiple cultural groups without necessarily compromising their cultural identity with objective being to exploit the cultural diversify nature of their environment through acquiring multiple KSAOs that will help promote their activity.

H2d. Broad role repertoire significantly increases the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities

VARIABLES	(1) Marginal effects
Broad role repertoire	0.0441*** (0.0507)
education	-0.0102 (0.105)
Age	-0.535*** (0.183)
Branch of activity	-0.270** (0.130)
Employment option	0.0522 (0.147)
Constant cut1	-3.883*** (0.988)
Constant cut2	-2.907*** (0.971)
Constant cut3	-2.173** (0.968)
Constant cut4	-1.335 (0.959)
Constant cut5	-0.793 (0.949)
Constant cut6	-0.405 (0.945)
Observations	120

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Considering broad role repertoire as a variable for boosting the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities by owner-managers of micro and small businesses at early-stage, results show a 4.4 percentage points more likely for broad role repertoire to increase the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities. The supposed indicated increase is being accompanied with a high level of significance (0.01 significance level), a representation of the much importance this variable upholds as to ensuring the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities in a multicultural setting. This results calls for more importance to be accorded by owner managers of small businesses, as to building a more continuous acceptable behaviour towards the different multiple cultural groups given their entrepreneurial orientation.

The level of education, age and branch of activity given their respective control functions represent 1.02, 53.5 and 27 percentage points less likely to boost the influence of broad role repertoire on the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities. The branch of activity despite its negativity appears to demonstrate an important effect as to reconciling differences given its significance at 0.05 level. Employment preference tends out to be the lone control factor having a 5.22 percentage points more likely to prove its ability in enhancing the relationship between broad role repertoire and the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities.

V. Conclusion

Growing a young business at early-stage in a dynamic, uncertain and multicultural environment; requires young owner-managers to adopt strategic entrepreneurship behaviour distinct from other business professionals. Individual entrepreneurs are required to organize their firms in a manner whereby; they can better scan their environments permitting the recognition, evaluation and exploitation of opportunities (Alvarez and Barney, 2005; Morris et al., 2013; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000). Unlike a monoculture and bicultural environment with limited cultural habits from which customers' needs can be met; a multicultural environment consist of several cultural habits where, by carrying an intensive scan across cultures will lead to the identification of unsatisfied customers' needs demanding some attention.

Exploiting such opportunities will require developing multicultural competencies being the acquisition of multiple knowledge, skills, abilities and other experiences in a given domain of operation (Aleksandra, 2014; Al-Shammari and Al Shammari, 2018; Newman et al., 2019).

Operating a newly created business nowadays should not be limited within the so called existing routines of general business management. Avenues for building existing knowledge should be explored through the acquisition of multicultural competencies. This, will enhance the identification of more exploitable business opportunities having innovative orientations for the expected growth of small businesses during the early years of their existence. We have integrated entrepreneurial alertness and the knowledge spill-over theory to address the gap by establishing multicultural competencies unique for the identification of entrepreneurial opportunities. The developed scales will enable entrepreneurship learners to evaluate the effectiveness of their entrepreneurial endeavours. This, will go a long way to enhance the entrepreneurial attitudes and behaviours of newly created business operators striving to grow their firms. Holding on our study, we believe on a first note that; it will ignite future research on the role of multicultural education on entrepreneurship behaviours. Secondly, this study can solicit further research on examining the development of effective avenues for the recognition of more entrepreneurial opportunities.

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